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INTERNAL CHALLENGES AND PLANNING IN CREATING INDONESIA AS THE AXIS OF THE WORLD MARITIME ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

The achievement of the vision of the world maritime axis must be directly proportional to the conditions of national stability. In other words, successful maritime development can only run well if it is supported by strong defense and security, both nationally, regionally, and globally. Thus, the Indonesian Navy as the main component of national defense at sea which carries out the functions of deterrence, enforcement, and restoration of national security is obliged to carry out its duties to uphold national sovereignty at sea, maintain the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI) and safeguard the safety of the entire nation. The research method used is literature review research with a descriptive approach. The result is In realizing this vision of the world's maritime axis, the role of all components of the nation is needed to realize a strong national defense by taking into account the country's geopolitics and geo-economy with a maritime perspective so that a national defense development plan with a maritime perspective is needed.

KEY WORDS:

Indonesia, Maritime Economy, Internal Challenges.

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Introduction

The election of President Joko Widodo (Jokowi) in the 2014 presidential election was the first step for a new development style of Indonesian governance. The idea of the Global Maritime Axis campaigned by Jokowi since 2014 has become the policy agenda of his government which has big aspirations to return Indonesia to its glory as a seafaring nation (Jalesveva Jayamahe). This policy at the same time emphasizes that during its 2015-2019 government span, Indonesia emphasized the development of the maritime sector in various aspects (Nainggolan, 2015). Various efforts have been made by the president to realize this goal, starting from building a world-class sea highway on the main islands, with at least 24 ports in Indonesia including Periuk, providing more fishing vessels, reforming the fish trading system to developing human resources and some other things. This shows the seriousness of the president in realizing Indonesia as the world's maritime axis.

One of the president's ideas refers to its geographical conditions. As explained in a book written by the Geospatial Information Agency supported by the Indonesian Geographical Association Indonesia has a wider water area than the mainland, which is 6,315,222 km², the length of the archipelago coastline is 99,093 km, and the number of islands has been standardized by the National Team. The standardization of the Topography of the Earth is 13,466 islands. Coupled with the geographical location flanked by the Indian and Pacific oceans as well as the Asian and Australian continents which contain large amounts of natural resource wealth. This condition also has implications for making Indonesia a cross-road for international trade.

Jokowi's maritime policy is a new breakthrough in the history of Indonesian government. This new breakthrough has implications for Indonesia in the future in terms of the economy as its national interest. Supported by its position as an international trade cross, it becomes a large economic resource if it is utilized optimally through the world's maritime axis. Jokowi targets the success of the world's maritime axis, progress from a lower-middle-level country with a per capita income of US\$ 3,592 in 2015 to an upper-middle-income country with a per capita income of US\$ 10,000, in 2045 (Nainggolan, 2015). In other words, if the world's maritime axis policy is achieved as expected, Indonesia will be able to be sovereign from an economic point of view.

But the hope of realizing the world's maritime axis must be hampered. This was due to several challenges both external and internal. In this paper the author will focus on discussing internal challenges. In general, the authors group them into two, namely internal challenges from a managerial and operational perspective. For this purpose, in general the systematic discussion of this paper includes the approaches and concepts that will be used to explain this case. The Integrated Coastal and Ocean Management Approach which is the result of the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) as the main approach and supporting concepts using the National Interest put forward by Hans J. Morgenthau. The discussion continued with maritime managerial challenges in Indonesia. Then added to the challenges of maritime operations, examples of internal challenges from these two aspects will also be given. At the end, a general summary of this discussion will be given.

The current government's vision is an opportunity as well as a challenge that must be followed up with careful and appropriate steps by the TNI in general, and the Navy (TNI AL) in particular, to support the government's program in developing Indonesia as the world's maritime axis. In accordance with the development program that has been launched by the government, the aspect of maritime defense and security is an important matter that must be addressed because security in the Indonesian sea area is a determining factor for the success of the government's program.

Practically, the achievement of the vision of the world maritime axis must be directly proportional to the conditions of national stability. In other words, successful maritime development can only run well if it is supported by strong defense and security, both nationally, regionally and globally. Thus, the Indonesian Navy as the main component of national defense at sea which carries out the functions of deterrence, enforcement and restoration of national security is obliged to carry out its duties to uphold national sovereignty at sea, maintain the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI) and safeguard the safety of the entire nation. In order for these tasks to be carried out optimally, the collaboration of the concept of building the

strength of the Indonesian Navy and the concept of maritime development must be in line, integrative, complement and strengthen one another.

And also the hope of realizing the world's maritime axis must be hampered. This was due to several challenges both external and internal. In this paper the author will focus on discussing internal challenges. In general, the authors group them into three, namely internal challenges from a managerial, operational perspective and the military perspective. For this purpose, in general the systematic discussion of this paper includes the approaches and concepts that will be used to explain this case. The Integrated Coastal and Ocean Management Approach which is the result of the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) as the main approach and supporting concepts using the National Interest put forward by Hans J. Morgenthau. The discussion continued with maritime managerial challenges in Indonesia. Then added to the challenges of maritime operations, examples of internal challenges from these two aspects will also be given. At the end, a general summary of this discussion will be given.

Conceptual Basis

To further study the internal challenges in realizing Indonesia as a world maritime axis, the author uses an integrated coastal and ocean management approach and the concept of national interest. The approach to managing coastal and marine areas in an integrated manner is a new approach, one of the results of the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992 which was listed in Agenda 21 chapter 17 as a work plan in the 21st century.

Integrated marine space management includes sectoral integration, scientific integration, and ecological integration. Sectoral integration consists of horizontal integration, namely coordination of tasks, authorities and responsibilities between sectors or government agencies at the government level and vertical integration, namely coordination in vertical integration occurs between levels of government starting from village, sub-district, district, and so on. Next, the integration of science means that the management of coastal and marine areas is carried out based on an interdisciplinary approach involving various fields of knowledge. Meanwhile, ecological integration refers to coastal and marine areas composed of various ecosystems(Sunyowati, 2010).

There are four levels and four aspects in an integrated marine and coastal area management approach. The four levels include national policy instruments, basic law, procedural law, and regional regulations regarding the management of coastal and marine areas (GEF/UNDP/IMO Regional Program for Prevention of Marine Pollution in the East Asian Seas 1999)(Sunyowati, 2010). Meanwhile, the four aspects according to Rudyanto (2004, in Lekipiouw 2010) include: (1) integration between various sectors and the associated private sector, (2) integration between various levels of government, from the center to districts/cities, sub-districts and villages, (3) integration between the use of terrestrial and marine ecosystems, and (4) integration of science and technology and management. The goal of an integrated marine and coastal area management approach is to achieve sustainable development in the marine sector.

Based on this approach, the internal challenges faced by Indonesia in realizing the world maritime axis are problems in sectoral integration, especially horizontal integration between sectors or government agencies at the government level due to overlapping tasks and principals between maritime law enforcement agencies. This then has implications for the levels and principles in the management of coastal and marine areas in an integrated manner. Horizontal integration that is less integrated results in the non-fulfillment of principles in the management of coastal and marine areas in an integrated manner, thereby hindering the achievement of sustainable development in the marine sector which will affect the achievement of Indonesia's aspirations as the world's maritime axis.

The next concept used is the concept of national interest. The definition of national interests is very broad, giving rise to many definitions of national interests. One of the most well-known definitions of national interests is the definition of national interests put forward by the main theorist of classical realism in the study of international relations, Hans. J Morgenthau. According to Morgenthau, national interest is the main pillar to support a country's foreign policy and international politics(Mas' oed, 1990). Mohtar Mas' oed (1990) explained that the minimum meaning of Morgenthou's concept of national interest is survival, which in this context is the

survival of the country. The state must be able to maintain its territorial integrity (physical identity), maintain its political economy regime (political identity), and maintain norms, values, religious, linguistics, and so on (its cultural identity).

Making Indonesia the world's maritime axis is a form of Indonesia's national interest. President Joko Widodo's policy to make Indonesia a maritime axis is a form of Indonesia's survival by maintaining its territorial integrity (physical identity) and maintaining its political-economic regime (political identity). By making Indonesia the world's maritime axis, this will increase the integrity of Indonesia's waters and marine areas and increase the optimization of the utilization of marine products and the economy of the Indonesian people, bearing in mind that Indonesia already has great economic potential in the marine sector.

The world maritime axis policy is included in the type of secondary interest based on the division of types of national interest according to Morgenthau because realizing Indonesia as a world maritime axis requires a long time and process, but its results and functions can be felt in the future in a long period of time. In addition, to achieve the realization of Indonesia as a world maritime axis, it does not require violent steps such as war, but by using maritime diplomacy.

Managerial Challenges for the Realization of the World Maritime Axis

The management of marine resources in Indonesia is carried out by many agencies under the government. The working mechanism of the agency will automatically become a supporter or obstacle to realizing the ideals of the world maritime axis proclaimed by Jokowi. This means, in terms of maritime affairs, Indonesia adheres to a multi-agent system. This form is an institutional system where there is more than one institution that interacts at the same time to achieve or solve the same problem (Nainggolan, 2015). In Indonesia's maritime affairs, there are at least 12 agencies where each has main tasks and functions as well as program activities related to the management of marine resources. In the article on Marine Resources Control System Planning by the Directorate of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, it is stated that these agencies include: 1). Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DKP); 2). National Land Agency (BPN); 3). Ministry of Environment (KLH); 4). Department of Energy and Mineral Resources (ESDM); 5). Ministry of Finance (MoF); 6). Directorate General of Customs and Excise; 7). Directorate General of Immigration; 8). Department of Transportation; 9). Ministry of Forestry and Plantation; 10). Indonesian National Army Navy; and 11). Sea Police.

In marine matters, the agency's field of work is covered by at least 10 statutory regulations as stated in the same article issued by the Directorate of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries. These laws include: 1). Law Number 5 of 1983 concerning the Exclusive Economic Zone; 2). Law Number 9 of 1985 concerning Fisheries; 3). Law Number 17 of 1985 concerning Ratification of the 1982 United Nations Convention concerning the Law of the Sea; 4). Law Number 5 of 1990 concerning Conservation of Living Natural Resources and their Ecosystems; 5). Law Number 21 of 1992 concerning Shipping; 6). Law Number 24 of 1992 concerning Spatial Planning; 7). Law Number 6 of 1996 concerning Indonesian Waters; 8). Law Number 23 of 1997 concerning Environmental Management; 9). Law Number 22 of 1999 concerning Regional Government; 10). Law Number 41 of 1999 concerning Forestry Principles. Whereas during Jokowi's administration, he issued Presidential Regulation Number 178 of 2014 concerning the establishment of the Maritime Security Agency (Bakamla) which was a transformation from the Maritime Security Coordinating Body (Bakorkamla) which only had coordinating duties. This transformation has implications for Bakamla's authority, which extends to the authority to take action against all forms of crime at sea (Nainggolan, 2015).

Main Duties and Functions (tupoksi) of these agencies as stated in the article Planning for Marine Resources Control Systems by the Directorate of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries as follows:

Institue	Main Duties and Functions
Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries	Help accelerate the process of economic recovery by efforts to overcome the problem of poverty in coastal communities, especially fishermen and fish farmers as well as the utilization of marine resources.
Ministry of Environment	Formulate policies in the field of conservation as well as coordinate and supervise them, including changing people's attitudes to life and supporting the concept of sustainable development and the Earth Charter.
Department of Transportation Directorate General (Ditjen) HUBLA	Carry out the formulation and implementation of policies, preparation of norms, standards, procedures and criteria, provision of technical guidance and supervision as well as evaluation and reporting in the field of patrols and security, law enforcement and advocacy, orderly shipping, disaster management and underwater work, facilities and infrastructure.
Ministry of Finance Directorate General of Customs (DJBC)	Carry out government functions related to trade facilitators, community protectors and revenue collectors. In terms of trade facilitators, DGCE tries to reduce the high economic costs associated with releasing goods and create a conducive trade climate by preventing illegal trade.
Department of Energy and Mineral Resources (ESDM)	Having policies to improve performance to realize good and clean governance (good governance).
Departemen Kehutanan dan Perkebunan (Ministry of Forestry and Plantation)	Manage natural resources, maintain their carrying capacity and utilize them through conservation, rehabilitation and savings by applying environmentally friendly technologies. Gradually delegating central government authority to regional governments in selective natural resource management and environmental preservation. Utilizing it by taking into account the preservation of environmental functions and balance, sustainable development, economic and cultural interests of local communities, as well as spatial planning regulated by law. Implementing indicators of preservation of renewable capabilities in the management of renewable natural resources.
Polisi Air (Polair)	Fostering and carrying out the functions of the National Maritime Police in the context of serving, protecting, nurturing and maintaining public order and security and law enforcement in Indonesian territorial waters.
Tentara Nasional Indonesia	In accordance with Law No. 34 of 2004 article 9 namely carrying out the duties of the TNI in the field of defense, enforcing the law, maintaining maritime security in recognized jurisdictions, carrying out naval diplomacy to support foreign policy, building and developing the strength of the maritime dimension and implementing empowering the maritime defense area.

If you read at a glance the duties and functions of each agency above, editorially the words do not show similarities indicating overlap between them. However, if we take a closer look, there appears to be some overlapping authority between these agencies. Among them is the division of the function of controlling marine and fisheries resources in several agencies under the scope of different departments but in the realm of work in the same location, namely marine, as explained by the directorate of marine and fisheries. For example, in terms of fisheries being part of the duties and functions of the Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Council. Meanwhile, in matters of buying and selling (trade), including trade in marine products in the form of fish, it is within the scope of the main duties and functions of the Ministry of Finance, Directorate General of Customs and Excise. Furthermore, forestry matters including those related to mangrove forests and marine national parks are under the Ministry of Forestry and Plantations.

On the other hand, the Maritime Police is an institution based on law carrying out the function of investigating and investigating crimes with forensic support, and recognized by international law. Meanwhile, the Indonesian Navy is given the authority to pursue, arrest, investigate and investigate cases in the maritime domain. In addition, the presence of Bakamla also has the authority to act on crimes at sea after transforming from Bakorkamla. This transformation gave him wider authority, namely carrying out security and safety patrols in Indonesian waters and Indonesian jurisdiction (CNN Indonesia 2015, in Abraham Utama). At the same time, the existence of Bakamla raises pros and cons because it is considered that the main problem is not the shortage of the maritime sector but the lack of coordination between sectors. Wiratama (2015) emphasizes that existing institutions operate according to their respective duties and indicate the specific roles of each institution (specialization). It is this specialization role that must be strengthened through the coordination function meaning that coordination between agencies is very important to reduce the intensity of sectoral ego.

Operational Challenges for the Realization of the World Maritime Axis

In realizing the world's maritime axis, Indonesia does not only have to face managerial challenges related to overlapping authorities between government agencies but also has to face operational challenges such as issues of piracy and armed piracy at sea, violation of state boundaries and illegal fishing crimes (Rustam 2016).

Piracy and armed piracy at sea that occur around Indonesian waters will hinder the realization of the world's maritime axis due to Indonesia's unsafe maritime or maritime situation. This will result in high operational costs for ships because they have to go around shipping lanes to avoid the risk of piracy. In addition, it also results in high costs for ship and crew insurance premiums because pirates not only take the ship's cargo but also take hostages and hurt the crew (Ayuningtyas 2016). One of the cases of piracy and hijacking was experienced by 10 crew members of the Brahma 12 pilot boat. The crew of the Brahma 12 pilot boat along with a cargo of coal belonging to a mining company from Banjarmasin, South Kalimantan, were taken hostage by the Philippine terrorist group Abu Sayyaf in the Sulu sea area in 2016 (Kompas 2016). According to the International Maritime Bureau, Indonesian waters are the most dangerous place worldwide with the number of reported pirate attacks increasing by 37 per cent to 234 incidents in the first six months of 2003, compared to 171 in the same period last year (ABC Radio Australia 2012).

Another operational issue is the violation of state borders which in this context constitute sea boundaries which are also related to the problem of illegal fishing. Violation of national boundaries which is quite high and quite often occurs in Indonesia is a serious issue because it concerns the sovereignty of Indonesia's territory and the stability of Indonesia's maritime security. Based on the records of the Indonesian Navy, in 2007 there were 94 violations committed by Malaysian warships in Indonesian waters in just one year (Usman and Isnawita 2009, in Rustam 2016). Meanwhile, regarding illegal fishing cases, the Supreme Audit Agency (BPK) shows data on the potential income of the marine fisheries sector in Indonesia without illegal fishing reaching IDR 365 trillion per year. However, due to illegal fishing, according to calculations by the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, this income is only around IDR 65 trillion per year (Bakosurtanal 2015, in Rustam 2016). Indonesia's geographical condition as an archipelago with many beaches is one of the factors that makes Indonesia vulnerable to illegal fishing. Fishing with vulnerable points in the area located in the Arafuru Sea, Natuna Sea, north of North Sulawesi (Pacific Ocean), Makassar Strait, and West Sumatra (Indian Ocean) (Detik News 2009,

in Setyadi 2014). Tackling the problem of illegal fishing itself is still lacking due to a lack of facilities, funds and personnel for monitoring Indonesian waters.

As previously mentioned, if the maritime axis policy is a form of survival for Indonesia by maintaining its territorial integrity, in this context, its sea area is triggered by the issue of violation of state boundaries and maintaining its political-economic regime to minimize illegal fishing, optimize the utilization of marine resources, and take advantage of Indonesia's position as an international trade route to increase per capita income.

TNI AL Strategy to Support the Vision of the World Maritime Axis

According to Rosabet Moss Kanter, the notion of world class is the highest standard in any aspect in order to be able to compete, and give birth to a social class with the ability to control resources and operate them far beyond borders and across a wide area (Kanter, 2002). Meanwhile, according to the Merriam Webster Dictionary, world class is the caliber or highest level in the world. Based on the definitions mentioned above, it can be concluded that the definition of a world-class TNI AL is a TNI AL that is able to present its strength in various parts of the world (Marsetio, 2014).

To be able to make a maximum contribution to Indonesia's development to become a PMD, the Indonesian Navy must have the appropriate strengths and capabilities to respond to the challenges that occur in the existing strategic environment. Therefore, the Indonesian Navy needs to build its strength and capabilities on a par with the navies of other developed countries. Naval history researcher, Anthony Bruce, Policy Director at the British Prime Minister's Advisory Committee and William Cogar, professor of naval history at the United States Naval Academy concluded, in any country, the navy is always required to be able to support the country's national interests (Anthony Bruce, 1998). Under these conditions, since its formation, the navy has been demanded to have the quality of a world-class navy. This is also relevant to the theory of the universal traditional role of the navy put forward by Ken Booth, traditionally the navy has three roles, namely the role of military, diplomacy and constabulary (Booth, 1977).

The role of the military is formed because of the character of militancy as an armed force, the role of diplomacy is carried out because of implementing the country's political goals and the role of the constabulary is related to the enforcement of national law and ratified international law and the protection of territorial sovereignty and the natural resources contained therein. This explanation reinforces the opinion that the formation of a qualitative navy must be able to carry out this universal role. If the navy has been able to fulfill the demands of its duties according to its universal role in securing national interests within and outside the region, then in terms of quality it can be said that the navy is world class (World Class Navy).

Planning for Strength Development of the Indonesian Navy

The implementation of the duties of the Indonesian Navy must be carried out in accordance with applicable laws and state political policies. This force development plan is formed through extracting the need to carry out the universal role of the Navy including military, diplomatic and constabulary roles, which are applied based on the interests of the use of force so that it can be projected in all areas of Indonesia's interests. To be able to carry out its duties, the TNI AL must be supported by forces capable of responding to all challenges along with the dynamics of the strategic environment. It is this strength that is expected to realize the vision and mission of the Indonesian Navy, as previously explained, so that accurate planning is needed to produce the ideal force.

On the other hand, the existence of the factor of availability of resources causes the state to need to set priorities within the development framework, so that the development of the Indonesian Navy which is an integral part of the national development framework must also select priorities without ignoring the principle of achieving goals. Based on a capability-based planning basis, the Indonesian Navy has planned the ideal projection of the Navy's strength needed to achieve the ability to protect national interests from various threats that may occur throughout the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. From this analysis, a posture requirement is formed that must be realized in 2024, with details of 274 KRI, 137 aircraft, and 890 marine combat equipment.

On the other hand, Indonesia's state defense budget is still not able to fully realize this power. Therefore, modifications to the calculations and planning for the development of the Indonesian Navy are currently carried out with reference to capability-based planning and taking into account budgetary capabilities. In the end, the development of the capabilities and strength of the Indonesian Navy is carried out in stages and is directed at targets that refer to urgent priorities and needs. The inability of the budget to fulfill this power can result in a reduction of the need for strength development that has been planned based on the previous ideal capability based planning. The provisional final posture approved by the government and planned in the Minimum Essential Force (MEF) development program for the main defense component until 2024 for the sea dimension is 151 KRI, 54 aircraft, and 333 marine combat equipment.

The process of realizing the strength development that has been planned, will be carried out through programs in the form of new acquisitions or procurement, rematerialization or maintenance, revitalization or capacity building and relocation or transfer of functions. The procurement process is carried out in accordance with applicable laws and regulations, for example in the form of procurement of defense equipment from within the country, joint production at home or abroad (joint production), offsets (domestic content), as well as forms of trade off compensation (trade tradeoffs), while sources or funding mechanisms come from the State Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBN), Domestic Loans (PDN), Foreign Loans (PLN) or Export Credit (KE) and Defense Industry Technology Development (Bangtekindhan).

The Indonesian Navy is currently synergizing with various law enforcement agencies at sea by carrying out law enforcement to create law and order at the sea, such as the Water and Air Police, the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries and the Directorate General of Sea Transportation. The efforts of the Indonesian Navy are in line with the steps taken by the government which has currently formed and strengthened the Maritime Security Agency (Bakamla), which is the partner of the Indonesian Navy in ensuring security and safety in Indonesia's maritime territory. It is hoped that cooperation between stakeholders in the sea will increase through coordination between Ministries and Agencies, integration of maritime information and surveillance systems, integrated operations management, and structuring of various regulations to increase effectiveness and eliminate overlapping activities or authorities.

Conclusion

Indonesia's national interest in strengthening and improving the economy through the world's maritime axis faces several internal challenges from a managerial and operational perspective as previously described. Overlapping duties and functions between maritime management sectors, lack of coordination between sectors and rising sectoral ego are major challenges from a managerial perspective. Meanwhile in the operational realm, the lack of infrastructure to support maritime operations due to a lack of funds, rampant crime in the maritime sector such as piracy, illegal fishing, violation of national borders, and piracy are a big challenge for the realization of the world's maritime axis. On the other hand, the role of each sectoral should be a supporter of this policy, on the contrary, it becomes an obstacle to its implementation. It is better if horizontal integrity between sectors through integrated coordination is a concern supported by infrastructure supporting the performance of each sector, especially in terms of security and maritime patrols. This is none other than for the realization of Indonesia as the world's maritime axis.

The problems, challenges and tasks of the Indonesian Navy in the future are closely related to the dynamics of development in an increasingly complex and difficult to predict strategic environment both globally, regionally and nationally. The sustainability of maritime development in the framework of realizing Indonesia as the world's maritime axis is highly dependent on security stability in the territorial waters of Indonesia's national jurisdiction and in the region. The Indonesian Navy as the main component of national defense at sea has made maximum efforts to increase its strength and capabilities so that it can carry out its duties and roles in the field of national defense at sea and support government policies, especially in developing the maritime sector. As an archipelagic country with a strategic position and faced with a very dynamic strategic development environment, it is imperative for us to have a strong and modern Navy so that we are able to face every threat to the nation in the future which will be even bigger, more complex, dynamic and multi-dimensional.

In realizing this vision of the world's maritime axis, the role of all components of the nation is needed to realize a strong national defense by taking into account the country's geopolitics and geo-economy with a maritime perspective, so that a national defense development plan with a maritime perspective is needed. Therefore, a strategic plan is needed for the development of the country's maritime defense that collaborates all potential national defense capabilities. In order to realize the strategic plan, it is necessary to have consistency in the development of maritime defense with an integrated, integrated, organized and sustainable planning between TNI dimensions, ministries and other government institutions, and stick to the principles of transparency and accountability through the empowerment of all the potential exist synergistically and optimally.

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